

Software Migration and Architecture Evolution to Industrial Platforms: A Multi-Case Study

Technical Report

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This technical report provides an extended version of the paper *Software Migration and Architecture Evolution with Industrial Platforms: A Multi-Case Study* [22]. Here, we provide a case study protocol and detailed model description for this paper. The case study protocol is based on the template proposed by Brereton et al. [7].

1 Background and Motivation

The present research resulted as an extension of previous work on supporting architectural decisions based on quality attributes, and research on software ecosystems. Specifically, it is motivated by the objective of supporting architecture-driven software migration into a cloud or IoT/edge ecosystem.

Modern software systems are expected to evolve to satisfy the changing needs of their users and the changes in the technical environment, and remain economically viable [19, 6, 9]. Software architecture lies at the core of the evolution process. The architecture reflects not only its structure and behaviour, but also its constraints: the architecture specifies a system’s possible functionality and the quality attributes it can (or can not) fulfill [10, 4]. Accordingly, correct understanding and representation of the architecture are fundamental for a clear evolution process [19]. Failure to do so results in “code decay”, i.e. a drift away from the original architecture that erodes its performance and qualities [11].

At the same time, software engineering practice has in the past decades moved away from monolithic, in-house developed applications to using the offerings provided by collaborative platforms such as software ecosystems, the

cloud, and the Internet of Things (IoT). These platforms, and the subject of the migration of legacy software into them, have become subjects of dedicated research (e.g., [13, 17, 28, 23, 8]). Major cloud platform providers, such as Amazon Web Services (AWS) also provide some guidance in their publications (e.g., [1, 18, 3, 21]). Any migration process involves a number of options influenced by various parameters, from the narrow technical to business and financial considerations, which impact one another. The process begins with the discovery and assessment of available options in the new environment, followed by a decision on which “migration path” to follow (moving only the infrastructure with or without refactoring, moving the entire application, not moving, etc.). The first step, once the decision to move has been taken, is to rearchitect both the parts that are to be moved, as well as those that may remain unaffected, so that they can remain interoperable, followed by the concrete implementation of the chosen designs.

While the new platforms offer many advantages, their use presents a number of challenges for the software architect. First, these platforms are characterised by a large number of offerings of a highly dynamic nature; the growth, change, and turnover of offerings is so rapid that oversight quickly exceeds the personal experience of any individual. Automated tools and repositories are frequently provided to search the platforms, but the architect is usually still required to manually parse documentations of potentially “interesting” offerings. Architects have to choose from a large number of similar or competing solutions without necessarily having an insight into their workings, or their position in the wider technical environment; resulting in dependencies to unreliable, or ill-maintained, third-party software. Modern frameworks and platforms already provide many features that automate deployment, scaling, execution; [15] the choice of such a framework essentially includes the choice of tools, which has now become the architect’s responsibility; just as the monitoring/operating/feedback/update functions.

Second, the new technologies facilitate the creation of distributed systems-of-systems, which are deployed across various platforms, and which are required to integrate a number of heterogeneous data sources, software products, clients, etc. Individual applications are being replaced by ecosystems of services in an API economy [15]. As a result, the specification of interfaces, deployment constraints, and architecting for modularity and portability are of paramount importance. These factors combine to present an architect with the problem of a) discovering the environment parameters relevant to a project, b) designing an architecture to optimize for the target environments, and c) managing and maintaining that across a lifecycle that may see significant change in the parameters first defined in a). In each case, the architect’s decisions are heavily dependent on context—best practices for a specific application domain, available products and technologies, relevant regulations, desired qualities, and so on. All these constantly change over time and across different use cases and platforms.

This study aims to contribute towards filling this gap by providing a lightweight and reusable approach that enables architects to perform an exploratory

analysis of their options in a structured manner that ensures compliance with a minimal set of requirements. The focus lies not on detailed implementation, but on providing “just enough architecture” [12] for the broad outlines and main design decisions of a project—e.g., programming languages, technologies, architectures—that once taken involve are “costly to change” [15]. Based on three actual industrial products demanding significant architectural evolution, we performed a multi-case study to derive common requirements, elements and relationships of an architecture knowledge model, which was then used to support software architects in migration and, more generally, in software evolution scenarios.

From personal experience, previous work, and study of the relevant literature, we gathered a number of studies and manuals, beginning with the relatively narrow context of migration to a cloud platform, but these dealt mostly with the process as such rather than architecture aspects. Some work had been done on migration patterns (e.g., “forklift” or “hybrid multi-cloud” etc.) but this was not translated into a method to actually implement these and optimize a legacy system’s architecture, whether during a legacy-to-cloud migration or during the re-architecting of a cloud application into a distributed system extending across several deployment environments (other cloud platforms, IoT/edge platforms, etc). Our research is an attempt to combine the results of extant research into a useable model, and test whether and how that knowledge can be applied in scenarios from actual industrial practice.

2 Design

The research is designed as a holistic, multi-case study [27, 25]. The context examined is that of architecture evolution in a software migration scenario. The scope of the model we develop is a software system undergoing migration; as a result, the unit of analysis is not only the system itself, but also the target and origin environment(s) involved in each case.

The aim of the case study is to progressively evolve and refine a model that can represent the elements that play a role during the evolution process. As elements we define any object that has a distinct and self-contained identity, and can be used as a conceptual unit. This can include individual software products, technologies, protocols, programming languages, functional and non-functional requirements, licenses, etc.

The model must be detailed enough to represent the case study context, while generic enough to avoid overfitting. Ideally, it should be able to represent any software evolution scenario. The level of granularity is chosen at the software product rather than the code level, as it is expected to be used in a software ecosystem-based environment, where brownfield development will be the norm.

The main facilities offered by the model would be the management of knowledge, by creating a central knowledge repository that can be used to represent any software product, and more importantly the exploitation of knowledge, by exploiting the links between elements to select subsets based on specific criteria.

This would allow the architect to browse for “suitable” offerings (i.e., having a desired set of functional and non-functional attributes) for each step of the evolution process; if such were not found, or were not available, the model should be able to provide suggestions for adaptation of existing offerings, or the development of new ones, by exploiting paths that link two functional elements through conceptual elements (e.g., software architecture).

Based on these parameters, we define the following Research Questions:

- **RQ1:** defining a minimal set of elements and relationships required by software architects to sufficiently represent and specify a software system at a relatively high abstraction level suitable for “just enough” architecting

This question involves defining a number of attribute sets for describing an application: its business capabilities, technologies used in implementation, specific architecture patterns implemented, interfaces, etc. An application may also include (reuse) third-party offerings, which are also included as components, and need in turn to be described as applications. The extent of detail in the attribute sets can vary, since available documentation may be partial or out-of-date. Too much detail can even be unnecessary; for example, if we want to use a Java library for logging, we don’t really need to know its internals, only what it does and what it requires. As a result, this representation includes two related but somewhat distinct collections: those that describe an application as it is perceived (and reused) by the external world, and those that describe its internal structure (and are relevant during re-architecting).

- **RQ2:** defining a minimal set of elements and relationships required to represent the context of software evolution, and particularly in the case of migration to a new platform

This question involves defining a number of attribute sets for describing two things: a platform, which in a migration context is essentially a collection of constraints and available offerings, and the migration/evolution process itself, which involves a search for compatible solutions through different avenues of approach (e.g., via architecture patterns or compatible technologies). We avoided defining a specific process or migration case as described in the literature, in order to leave the architect free to make his own choices; the model is conceived of as an aid to the process, not as a blueprint for it. Instead we focused on providing the architect with a limited set of relevant or suitable solutions for the given context of each decision during that process, bearing in mind that many migration decisions involve the search for equivalent offerings that fulfil an identical (or almost) capability, subject to a number of (business, technology, legal, etc.) constraints.

- **RQ3:** to investigate how the models resulting from RQ1 and RQ2 can be used to support architectural decisions

This question is part of the step-by-step evolution of the model, which was adapted at each iteration to support our case studies. At the same time, we

investigated how the available knowledge represented in the model could best be organized and presented to the architect, so that it could provide usable guidance (per RQ2).

In designing the models and their graphical representation, we inevitably drew some inspiration from the widely used UML2 modelling language, particularly the component diagrams. However the domain we examined is sufficiently different, and any similarities with UML notation should be disregarded.

3 Case Selection

The cases we required to evolve and validate our model need to fulfill the following criteria:

1. They need to be fairly typical examples of the software migration context, involving extensive architectural evolution; e.g. a simple “forklifting” approach to migration to the cloud was insufficient.
2. They need to be fairly typical examples of industry systems, and interesting from a research standpoint in terms of size and complexity, so that each step of the evolution process depends on a number of factors, deriving from different domains, both functional and non-functional.
3. They need to be accessible for research, with at least a modicum of documentation that allows a sufficiently detailed reconstruction of their structure and attributes; ideally, architects involved with them should be available for interviewing and feedback.

4 Case Study Procedures and Roles

4.1 Procedures

The case study was structured as an iterative process, preceded by a comprehensive literature survey. A first instance of the model was created following the survey, and based on initial suppositions on the requirements generated by the migration context.

This was then tested in the first case study, and the results from that used to refine the model by altering (merging or introducing new) elements and relationships until it could adequately support this first scenario. This model was then used in the second case, refined again, and then so on with the third case. Contact with experts involved in these systems was sought at the start of each case study, to clarify the context and their perception of the system, and afterwards to validate the resulting models.

At the end of this process, the necessary elements and relationships of the model had crystallized; a final iteration improved and clarified the model structure.

4.2 Roles of Participants

- *Konstantinos Plakidas*: Literature survey, model creation, testing, and evolution
- *Daniel Schall*: Industry domain expert, model testing
- *Uwe Zdun*: Domain expert, research supervisor
- Practitioners from *Siemens*: Domain experts, model testers

5 Data Collection

5.1 Data Collection Methods

This research included both first-degree and third-degree data collection as defined by [25].

Initial data consisted of established and peer-reviewed research literature on software architecture and software migration, practitioner contributions in the form of blogs or op-ed articles, and online documentations of common software products. We followed a *grounded theory* approach [26] in building up the first iteration of the model, mapping the concepts encountered in the literature to elements in our model, and populating a knowledge base based on that model. Multiple sources were used to ensure completeness and objectivity of our information. The first version of the model was built up iteratively over time until theoretical saturation had been reached.

During the case studies, data was drawn from documentation on the systems under examination, as well as interviews with the experts involved. This information went into the creation of model instances of these systems and of the platforms and/or the wider business and technical environments involved. Any missing domain elements not included in our initial knowledge base were added from literature and online documentation.

During the testing of the migration scenarios, gaps or inefficient modelling in the semantic representation of certain concepts were identified, and addressed through the modification of existing elements, or addition of new ones. With any change in the model structure, the knowledge base collection was updated accordingly.

The knowledge base and the subjects of the case studies were stored in a graph database (we used Neo4j ¹), but the model can in principle be mapped to any database.

5.2 Scenarios used as Case Studies

5.2.1 Geospatial Analytics System

The first scenario concerns a legacy system that performs geospatial analytics for large-scale infrastructure such as oil and gas pipelines, the electrical grid, or

¹<https://neo4j.com/>

water distribution systems [20]. The scenario goal was to support the application's migration into a cloud platform (Siemens MindSphere) [5, 2].

The legacy system follows a 3-tier architecture with a presentation, business logic and data storage layer. Originally, the system has been developed as an on-premises solution with SCADA integration in mind. Various components such as a middleware for task orchestration have been implemented in a monolithic fashion using the C++ language and the Qt framework. In addition, the open-source GeoServer² has been used to visualize GIS data, and the Oracle Database³ with the Oracle Spatial and Graph extension⁴ to store original image and geospatial layer (vector) data. These result in some limitations with respect to PaaS deployment. Finally, computer vision algorithms require GPU support, which is currently not available in the PaaS offerings.

As a result of the scenario requirements, we followed a hybrid migration scenario. Some parts of the system, such as the analytics services, remain in a local IT infrastructure supporting GPU computing. Presentation and in particular dashboarding capabilities are moved to the cloud. In this case, a decision was taken that GeoServer had to be retained in the target application regardless of any possible alternatives; and that a cloud-based storage and GUI had to be provided, while some elements of the application had to remain on-premises for legal reasons. This meant a hybrid migration pattern [17], where only part of the application is moved to the cloud, while the rest remains on-premises.

5.2.2 Water Management System

The second scenario concerns the evolution of a legacy Water Management System (WMS) application, that is tasked with optimizing the use of a water delivery system comprising reservoirs, pipes, valves, etc. It uses EPANET⁵ to model the pipe distribution system and perform the optimization, based on data provided via external sources a) in XML format and b) through a SCADA interface using the OPC-UA protocol. The application includes an orchestration component based on the .NET framework that is essentially a stateless middleware that manages requests to the EPANET DLL via Platform Invocation Services (P/Invoke), as well as a dashboard to present data and manage the system.

The task at hand involved the migration of WMS into MindSphere, and the refactoring of the application into the Microservices [14] architectural style. This case includes a similar migration aspect as the first scenario, but is more architecture-driven, requiring the splitting up the monolithic legacy application into a modular target application. The challenge here was to provide guidance as to how this decomposition is to be done, and manage the complexity of dealing with around 40 patterns related to the Microservice style.

²<http://geoserver.org/>

³<https://www.oracle.com/database/index.html>

⁴<https://www.oracle.com/technetwork/database/options/spatialandgraph/overview/index.html>

⁵<https://www.epa.gov/water-research/epanet>

5.2.3 Edge-Cloud Analytics System

In the third scenario the capabilities of a monitoring system (on-premises SCADA solution) have been extended with cloud connectivity. In particular, the SCADA system has been modelled as an edge platform with analytics capabilities. Analytics functions are provided as services that can be deployed either locally at the edge platform or in the cloud. Deployment decisions are continuously evaluated by monitoring quality-of-service parameters and platform utilization. Updates in the deployment can be (re-)engineered to prevent overload conditions or unacceptable latencies.

Such a decision is a non-trivial problem, since in order to maximize benefits, a set of applications, or parts of the same application, may have to be deployed on either one or both platforms. It furthermore depends not only on the functional and non-functional requirements of each application, but also on what resources are actually available in the platform. Both factors are dynamic: the requirements of an application can change, especially in the context of approaches such as *Continuous Delivery* (CD) [16], while the resources available in each platform also change over time, as they are utilized by other services and applications. The problem is therefore how to model a dynamic set of deployment options and make them available for automatic assignment to assist the systems engineer in distributing analytics services across cloud-edge platforms.

6 Analysis

Analysis of the model’s performance and subsequent modifications were based on three criteria:

1. *Completeness* of representation of the elements required during a migration process, as determined by the literature and the case studies
2. Ability of the model to *suggest solutions*, i.e., narrow down a small subset of possible, compatible options from the far larger set contained in the knowledge base, and suggest solutions that are not explicitly documented
3. *Understandability* and *usability* during the migration process by the average user

The model’s *completeness* as far as the conceptual level is concerned—reflected in our *domain knowledge* model—is ensured by a comprehensive literature study, and the mapping of the concepts encountered there to corresponding objects in the model following the grounded theory approach. The completeness in terms of a practical definition of the structure and attributes of the individual software product—reflected in our *software description* model—derived from the software documentation, but mostly from its practical validation during the case studies. After each case study, we analyzed the migration processes performed using the model, resulting in a further elaboration of the model structure, particularly the number and nature of elements in each knowledge domain set and the relationships between them.

The ability to *suggest solutions* is a basic requirement for the model’s usefulness in a migration scenario. It directly impacted the links between the various knowledge domain sets and between the software description model and the knowledge domain sets. It also had a strong impact, over successive iterations, on the composition of the *Constraints* and *Technology* domain set. The *Constraints* set proved particularly useful in rapidly narrowing down the options space to a small subset, while the *Technology* set often provided the main path(s) for establishing non-explicitly documented compatibility between offerings. Best results were achieved here when the *Technology* set was combined with the *Capabilities* and *Architecture* sets.

Understandability and *usability* are desired, but were secondary to the first criteria; we tried to keep the model to the minimum number of necessary elements, and used the most common occurring terms for the elements. To address variances in usage, we included the option of defining aliases for synonyms, acronyms, etc. The practical testing of the model during the first case revealed, among other things, the necessity of splitting between a general “knowledge domain” model and a “software description” model. Direct work with the model nevertheless remained difficult, as the number of elements impacting even the most simple evolution step can quickly grow into the dozens or hundreds.

7 Plan Validity

The literature used generally reflects state-of-the-art knowledge and common practices, while multiple sources were examined so that the various sources complemented one another and biases were ironed out. The mapping of the accumulated knowledge into a first model will undoubtedly have introduced a degree of personal bias, and may have been less than optimal. However, the subsequent evolution of the model was guided exclusively through the requirements emerging from the case studies, and validated empirically and through interaction with domain experts.

The end result is not final, pending more thorough testing in different contexts. It is also possible that alternative case studies in other domains will produce different requirements, or variant interpretations on the composition of the model.

We have also assumed that the model will be used with no preconceptions; the model itself was designed to be usable both by the experienced architect, who may only require it for one or two tasks, as well as by the novice, who will have little experience or understanding. This means that we do not prescribe a “solution process” that will lead to guaranteed results; we only provide a tool that can be used in such a process.

From the experience of conducting the case studies and expert feedback, we were forced to revise some initial assumptions:

- As we populated our model from the literature, we assumed that a common language between stakeholders exists, so that the same term (e.g., a *Capability* or *Pattern*) will be commonly understood and used in the same

way. In practice, this proved problematic, leading us to include an “alias” feature in the model to at least address variant naming. The problem of providing at least a short explanation of the terms used, however, remains, and can not be easily addressed at the model level.

- Practitioners using the model could quickly become overwhelmed by the number of elements and options when undertaking explorative steps into the knowledge base. This emerged particularly strongly in architecture-driven scenarios, where the users preferred to be given a template architecture as a basic guideline during the migration process. Originally it was assumed that the definition of structural patterns with a set of component types would be sufficient for the purpose, but in the event, we were forced to create explicit blueprints for architecture configurations. While reducing the user’s creative freedom, this boosted usability. The problem of limiting the user’s scope for exploration to relevant objects, while not at the same time negatively impacting the model’s flexibility, is a problem that can only be solved by abstracting and managing user interaction with the model.

8 Study Limitations

Using the model requires the investment of time and effort to understand both it, and the applications to be modelled in it. Indeed, populating the knowledge base is a time-consuming process, which can introduce errors. This is an inherent problem in all such approaches, and this study does not concern itself with architecture reconstruction. We hope to mitigate this problem by creating a tool that will abstract the model and ease the description of applications and concepts for the average user. Likewise we are forced to assume that the descriptions provided to populate the model are accurate and up-to-date.

The model can also not replace the architect: many decisions are the responsibility of the architect, since the selection of an “optimal” solution is rarely straight-forward. In the usual case, there were a number of options available, all of which meeting some of the requirements to a degree. Ideally, we should be able to provide a ranking of the importance and impact of the remaining mismatches, but this is problematic, as this can fluctuate greatly depending on context. So far, the model can only provide an overview of the context of a specific problem; it is left to the architect to evaluate it and make a choice. Likewise, the cumulative impact of such decisions is difficult to be assessed, and may only become apparent at the end of the evolution process. A tool based on the model could provide assistance here through data-driven machine-learning approaches, or a recommender feature.

9 Reporting

The work is intended to serve as a basis for a more systematic approach to architectural decision-making. It will help identify the main elements involved in the migration process, provide a structured approach to describing applications and platforms, and facilitate the navigation of complex environments based on functional and non-functional requirements.

We hope to build on the model and the insights gained to explore related questions that we could only touch upon in this work. We will develop a tool that abstracts the model and provides greater user-friendliness, with which we aim to refine the model with other scenarios in different contexts and with a broader variety of stakeholders, including both expert and novice architects, and developers. The tool will also allow the study of specific aspects that impinge indirectly on the model, and may lead to modifications or extensions thereof. This includes the optimization of workflow and representation of the knowledge to the architect, the analysis of impact of, and tradeoffs between, multiple quality attributes depending on context, and the implementation of traceability features for a decision process based on the model.

10 Course of the Study

The initial literature survey and creation of the first major version of the model took two months, December 2016 – January 2017.

The first case study, concerning a Geospatial Analysis System, was conducted over March and April 2017. This first study served as proof of the model’s validity. As a result, several iteration rounds of alterations to the model and testing took place until a satisfactory result was reached. This was followed by an evaluation stage that led to a second major version of the model.

The second case study, on an Edge-Cloud Analytics System, was conducted in May–June 2017, and the third, on a Water Management System, in July–September 2017. The basic structure of the model remained unaltered, but refinements were undertaken in the connections between knowledge domain sets, the representation of interfaces, and the structure of the *Architecture* set. Furthermore, the need for *templates* providing an architectural stub for concrete scenarios became apparent during the testing phase by the experts, and was tested in the Water Management System study.

The study was completed with a final evaluation phase in September–October 2017, which resulted in the final model presented in the next sections, along with characteristic examples of its use.

11 Domain Knowledge Model

The *domain knowledge* model is the result of our efforts to answer RQ2: a model that includes the elements (applications, application attributes, business concerns, etc.) involved in the migration process, and that allows the architect

to identify compatibilities and mismatches, and find solutions by exploiting the relationships between these elements. The resulting *domain knowledge* model is based on two types of objects (Figure 1): *Instance Elements* and *Type Elements*. The *Type Elements* serve to provide an ontology-like hierarchical structure for categorization, while the *Instance Elements* represent the leaves of the ontology, and specific instances of the categories.

Figure 1: The supertypes of the *domain knowledge* model

Following experimentation with various alternatives, we settled on five distinct knowledge sets: *Applications*, *Architecture*, *Technology*, *Constraints*, and *Capabilities*. *Applications* emerged from the fundamental need to model software products and their relations to one another, while *Architecture* provides the necessary link to software architecture concepts and methods. *Technology* was adopted as a shorthand for the implementation details in terms of protocols, languages, and standards. *Constraints* is used as a generic term for every “additional” constraint that may circumscribe the usage of a specific product (e.g., licensing or deployment restrictions), or define the parameters in which it should operate (quality attributes). The *Capabilities* set is less complex, it comprising simply a set of functionalities and capabilities which can be used to describe (or set as requirements for) a software product. Obviously this division is not immutable—pending further testing and elaboration—nor may it represent an optimal solution; in our case studies, however, and in structuring the model and discovering the relationships between the elements we found it practical.

Each of these sets is implemented in the domain model, and provided with types, instances, and relationships particular to it. Each *Instance Element* of a set can belong to one or more *Type Elements* of the same set. The hierarchy flows from the specific to the more abstract and generic. An example can be seen in Figure 2: the leaf node “PostgreSQL” of the *Applications* set is of the type “Object-Relational Database”, which in turn is of the type “Dataset Storage”, which is of the type “Data Store”.

The *Applications* set (Figure 3) is essentially the core of the *knowledge domain*, as it represents the actual software products. This is reflected in its relative complexity compared to the other sets, which are mostly used as attributes for the *Applications* instances. In addition, the *Applications* set serves to link the *domain knowledge* model with the *software description* model, as

Figure 2: Storage offerings provided in the *MindSphere* cloud platform, as imported in the *Neo4j* graph database. Instance Elements in red, Type Elements in yellow.

each *Applications* (Instances as well as Types) element has a corresponding *software description* instance.

In the *Applications* domain we distinguish between *Applications* proper and *Libraries*: an *Application* is a stand-alone product, and can be composed of both *Application* and *Library* instances, whereas a *Library* can only be used as part of an *Application*, can only be composed of other *Library* instances, and is closely associated with a set of *API* definitions from the *Technology* domain.

Relationships of instances within the domain are: *COMPATIBLE* denotes mutual compatibility between two domain instances, if documented; *VARIANT* denotes an application which is a variant of a specific baseline (e.g., .NET Core vs. .NET), while *EXTENDS* is used for product extensions and plugins that require another application to function; for versioning purposes, *VERSION OF* indicates a specific version of an application (e.g., version 2.11.0 of GeoServer), and *SUPERSEDED BY* links each new version or new application with its immediate predecessor.

REALIZES is used to indicate where a domain instance implements instances from the other domains. To use the previous example, because “Database” $\xrightarrow{\text{REALIZES}}$ “Data Persistence Capability”, and “Database” $\xrightarrow{\text{REALIZES}}$ “Data Query Capability”, it follows that “PostgreSQL”, as a subtype of “Database”, will also implement the same capabilities and have the corresponding *REALIZES* relationships to them. This allows the use of the *Capabilities* domain to search for suitable *Application* instances, as will be shown later. In the same manner, suitable applications that implement specific architecture elements, and libraries that implement specific technologies, can be found. This is of use during experimentation with different options during the evolution, where compatible solutions can be searched for by using links between different domains, or by

Figure 3: Model of the elements and relationships of the *Applications* set (in red), including its links to other sets (blue for *Architecture* instances, green for *Capabilities* instances, and yellow for *API* instances from the *Technology* set)

going up the typology chain to more generic solutions.

Figure 4: Model of the elements and relationships of the *Architecture* set (in blue), including its links to other sets (in different colours)

The *Architecture* domain (Figure 4) is composed of *Architecture Concept* instances, in turn grouped into *Architecture Type* categories. An *Architecture Concept* can be expressed as an *Architectural Pattern* or an *Architectural Style*. In the literature the terms are often used interchangeably, but we have opted to interpret *Architectural Style* as a more generic category, such as “Service-Oriented Architecture” or “Client-Server Architecture”, whereas an *Architectural Pattern* represents a concrete technical solution to a specific problem. As a result, an *Architectural Style* is linked to related *Architectural Pattern* instances in a one-to-many relationship. Each *Architecture* domain instance can also REALIZE a specific *Functionality*, or enhance (or negatively affect) one or more *Quality Attributes* from the *Constraints* domain.

The *Technology* domain (Figure 5) covers *Standards*, *Languages* and *Data Formats*, *Protocols*, and *API* definitions. Each domain element can realize *Capabilities*, *Architecture*, and *Quality Attributes* domain instances. Again there

Figure 5: Model of the elements and relationships of the *Technology* domain (in yellow), including its links to other domains (in different colours)

is a type hierarchy, while additionally an *API* can be composed of other *Technology* instances, and a *Standard* can be IMPLEMENTED by a *Language*, *Data Format*, or *Protocol*.

Figure 6: Model of the elements and relationships of the *Constraints* domain, including its links to other domains (in different colours)

The *Constraints* set (Figure 6) is divided into three different categories: *Licenses*, *Quality Attributes* such as Non-Functional Requirements (NFRs), and miscellaneous *Deployment Constraints* that may restrict the deployment of an application or application component (e.g., data privacy, hardware requirements, etc.). Additional categories of instances can be easily defined here, depending on how fine-grained distinctions are considered as suitable. For ease of use, we tried to keep it as minimal as possible.

Finally, the *Capabilities* set comprises only *Capability* instances, which can in turn be composed of other instances from the same set. The strength of the com-

position relationships can vary between “strong” (always included), “medium” (typically included), and “weak” (can be included).

Defining a specific set of knowledge elements (particularly in regards to *Capabilities*) proved a major issue, since both in the scholarly literature as well as among practitioners, the usage of specific terms is inconsistent or variously defined: different names may be used for the same concept, or different things may be grouped under the same term. For this reason, we made heavy use of the IS and ALIAS relationships defined in the *domain knowledge* model. We cannot claim to have resolved the issue, however, and in practice, the exact definition of each term will depend on those who use it.

12 Software Description Model

In answering RQ1, we developed a *software description* model, which represents the functional and non-functional context of an application when viewed as a stand-alone product. Each instance of *software description* makes use of *domain knowledge* elements, by combining them in a specific configuration that represents the implementation and attributes of the application in question. Each element of the *Applications* set must have a, more or less complete, *software description*.

Mirroring the *domain knowledge* domains, the *software description* model is subdivided into collections of objects:

- *Capabilities* collection: the business capabilities and functionalities that the application (or rather its components) realizes.
- *Components* collection: individual software products, either off-the-shelf from the *Applications* set or custom-developed, used in creating the specific application. This collection also includes the links between components, and their (and by extension the application’s) interfaces to the external world. Hence the *Components* collection also documents an application’s dependencies.
- *Architecture* collection: software architecture concepts such as patterns and styles, and the elements comprising them, that are used to structure the specific application.
- *Implementation Languages, Data Input, Data Output* and *Data Operations* collections: technologies used in the application and interaction with its environment.
- *Quality Attributes, Licenses, Deployment Constraints* collections: supplementary constraints on the application’s behaviour (NFRs) and reusability by third parties.

Since each *Component Instance* is linked to its own *software description*, any software product can be composed of other software products. The external

Figure 7: The *software description* model. *domain knowledge* entities are depicted as ovals, their local instances in a specific *software description* as hexagons. The latter are aggregated into collections. Interfaces are shown as circles. The boundary of the specific *software description* instance is shown as a striped grey line.

attributes of each (*Component Instance* are then available for the composite application, and can be linked to specific attributes of its *software description*. For instance, a database, which on its own REALIZES the “Data Persistence” *Capability*, can fulfill the same *Capability Instance* when used as a component.

For the same reason, a new *Application* instance can inherit the *software description* of its parent type(s) or previous versions. A new database would thus inherit the “Data Persistence” *Capability* from the “Database” type, while a relational database would also inherit SQL as the technology of the *Data Operations, Input, and Output* instances. A new version of an *Application* would, upon instantiation, be identical to the immediately previous one (linked with SUPERSEDED BY), and only the changes particular to that version would have to be altered. Likewise, in order to define a family of similar software products, an *Application* can be defined as a baseline with the common attributes, to which the specific products will be linked via VARIANT relationships. Any new variant would have to have *at least* the same features as the central baseline. The variants can be variously defined: variant implementations of the same specification by different partners, variant deployment configurations of the same product in

different platforms, variant versions for different hardware or software platforms, etc.

Bearing this in mind, the degree of detail and completeness of the *software description* can vary. While completeness is generally desired as it provides a complete set of the available options, it is not always necessary or required: third-party commercial products, for example, are usually reused as a unitary package, and their internals (i.e., the *Components* and *Architecture* collections) may be unknown. As long as the *software description* provides a product’s *external* interfaces and associations with all other domain elements (e.g., compatible technologies, functionalities realized, licenses, etc.), the product itself can be treated as a “black box” while still allowing its reuse as a component.

Likewise for a central baseline specification, only the *least common elements* need to be specified; anything not so specified would be left to be decided (within a given context provided by the chosen features and constraints) by others. This is of obvious significance in a software ecosystem environment, where products must ensure a minimum interoperability, but where the creativity of the community should be allowed free expression as far as possible.

13 Employing the Models

In the main paper, we have described the context in which the models were developed. Here we will provide examples from the cases we studied, as to how the models can be used to facilitate software migration.

The three scenarios, introduced in our main paper, were: the Geospatial Analytics System represented a “simple” migration scenario of a legacy monolith into a cloud platform, and a testbed for the first iteration of our model; the Water Management System represented a more complex migration scenario coupled with architectural evolution of the legacy monolith into microservice architecture; and the Edge-Cloud Analytics System was used to examine the extension of the model into application deployment on physical nodes and the Edge/IoT domain. These scenarios served as “proof-of-concept” and were used to improve the model’s ontology and test its ability to find a suitable outcome.

The process followed in each case involved three steps: the complete definition of a *software description* for the legacy application \mathcal{L} as well as any of its sub-components that we identified; the definition of a *software description* for the target environment \mathcal{E} , and finally, using the first two, the step-by-step definition of \mathcal{T} . For \mathcal{E} , a complete *software description* is not necessary, as the architect is not, for instance, interested in the exact structure of a platform; for our purposes in the context of a cloud or edge platform, we only need to model the available platform offerings (*Application* domain instances used as components, which ipso facto also define the available *Technology* domain instances) that can be (re-)used, and any constraints that affect applications deployed there.

The basic action provided by the models is the elementary matching process for exploiting the documented knowledge contained in the *knowledge domain*

in order to find and choose compatible elements. Building on that, we then demonstrate the model’s use in more complex migration scenarios.

The evolution process comprises a number of parameters. Based on the five domain sets of our model, the possible scenarios in formulating the *software description* of our new target application \mathcal{T} are:

- for the *Capability Instances* of the new application, $\mathcal{L}_{Capabs} \subseteq \mathcal{T}_{Capabs}$, unless a scenario involves extension and/or removal of application functionality (an *external decision*). In that case, the adaptation process usually begins with the elements that REALIZE the common set $\mathcal{L}_{Capabs} \cap \mathcal{T}_{Capabs}$, and the set $\mathcal{T}_{Capabs} \setminus \mathcal{L}_{Capabs}$ are dealt with after.
- for the instances of the *Constraints* domain, $\mathcal{T}_{Consts} \approx (\mathcal{L}_{Consts} \cup \mathcal{P}_{Consts})$, with appropriate adaptations due to *external decisions*.
- for the *Component Instances*, \mathcal{T}_{Comps} results from an adaptation process with heavy input from the architect: some \mathcal{L}_{Comps} may be retained because they are not deployed to the new target environment \mathcal{E} ; some $\mathcal{L}_{Comps} \in \mathcal{E}_{Comps}$ and can be directly reused; some \mathcal{E}_{Comps} are of the same type or have the same *Capabilities* as \mathcal{L}_{Comps} ($\notin \mathcal{E}_{Comps}$) and can be used to substitute the latter; and if none of this works, the general knowledge domain database can provide other solutions based on the *Architecture*, *Components*, and *Technology* views that allow the integration of incompatible \mathcal{L}_{Comps} into \mathcal{E} , or their replacement with other solutions not found in \mathcal{E}_{Comps} .
- for the instances of the *Technology* domain, \mathcal{T}_{Tech} is highly dependent on the *Component Instances* that REALIZE them. The platform technologies, \mathcal{E}_{Tech} , are effectively a constraint for the external \mathcal{T}_{Tech} as well (e.g., deployment to a cloud platform means that \mathcal{T} will have to be accessible via messaging or REST).
- for the *Architecture* domain instances, \mathcal{T}_{Arch} is precisely what has to be determined through the adaptation process. \mathcal{E}_{Arch} as such is usually irrelevant, but it may be associated with specific templates that can serve to create the initial stub \mathcal{T} (e.g., the PaaS element of \mathcal{E}_{Arch} could be connected to a basic *software description* of an elementary PaaS implementation).

Once the basic framework of \mathcal{T} has been defined, the migration process begins as shown in Sect. 4.2. Effectively it consists of an element-by-element, match-and-replace method: given the constraints imposed by \mathcal{T} , we test the fit of a given element from \mathcal{L} to the part of \mathcal{T} already defined. In the ideal case, the element will fit both \mathcal{T}_{Consts} and be compatible with the extant \mathcal{T}_{Comps} . If there are mismatches with \mathcal{T}_{Consts} , then the experimentation cycle begins until alternative solutions are found by using equivalent offerings from \mathcal{E}_{Comps} ; if there are mismatches with \mathcal{T}_{Comps} , bridging strategies are sought (i.e., paths that can link the given element with the \mathcal{T}_{Comps} in question) through the *Technology*,

Figure 8: Example for the use of the models to find suitable components for implementing the “Data Persistence” requirement for a *Target Application* \mathcal{T} by matching elements from a single domain, in this case, via *Capability* (green). Only partial instances are shown for simplicity.

Applications, or *Architecture* domains. The various views of the model thus function complementary to each other. The principle of selection hereby is the *least path distance*, i.e., the least amount of elements that are necessary to bridge a mismatch gap. With the placement of each new element, the *total* \mathcal{T} becomes more complex, but because the adaptation is broken down into individual decisions, each with its own context, the complexity is reduced to manageable levels.

14 Basic Model Features

A basic requirement for the models is to facilitate the discovery of suitable solutions by exploiting the explicit (direct) and implicit (indirect) links between elements. A rudimentary example is shown in Figure 8: the *Capability* requirement “Data Persistence” (an instance of the namesake *domain knowledge* element) can be realized via multiple *Application* domain types and instances, including various types of databases, file systems, etc. If, however, we refine the query with the stipulation that the same component shall also realize “Data Querying”, then we are led to choose a database. A more complex example is shown in Figure 9, where we provide a more precise definition of our “Data Persistence” element: it must be a database (indicating a specific *Application Type*), and is required to communicate with a given execution logic in SQL (*Interface* that implements the *Technology Instance* SQL). This produces multiple paths that link \mathcal{T} with possible compatible solutions such as PostgreSQL. In the optimal case, a solution would be an element that would realize all the requirements of \mathcal{T} (and only them). In practice, of course, that will rarely be the case, and comparisons between similar solutions, and decisions about tradeoffs will have to be made.

Figure 9: Example for the use of the models to find suitable components for implementing the “Data Persistence” requirement for a *Target Application* by matching elements from multiple domains: *Capability*, *Application Type*, *Technology*. Only partial instances are shown, and instance collections are omitted for simplicity.

Figure 9 also illustrates other features of the model, beginning with the distinction between global and local requirements: the “Local Database” component realizes the \mathcal{T} -global *Capability* “Local Data Persistence”, but locally it needs to realize an *Inter-Component Interface* (see Figure 7) with another component, using the *Technology* element SQL, a requirement that is not globally important for \mathcal{T} (it is not perceived by anyone who interacts with it). That is why the distinction between *External* and *Inter-Component* interfaces in the *software description* model is important: in order to use any software unit, for instance PostgreSQL, as a *Component* instance, we are not required to know its internal structure, but we do need to know how to interact with it.

The “Undefined Component” instances in Figure 9 are essentially a mock for “something” that simply provides (or requires, as the need may be) a specific interface, that is unknown to us. When the software unit is imported into the *software description* of \mathcal{T} , then its *External Interfaces* are also imported into it, and are available to be used as *Inter-Component Interfaces* with other components or again as *External Interfaces*, but this time for \mathcal{T} as a whole. This is a general principle: by importing an *Application* or *Library* as a *Component*, \mathcal{T} also inherits the attributes of its *software description*. It is left to the architect to decide which of the attributes apply globally for \mathcal{T} and which are only of local significance for the *Component* only.

The comparison between similar solutions can be carried out via matching as shown in Figure 9, but may often depend on factors that are not contained in the *domain knowledge* model; these can be attached to it through additional

views as metadata or annotations.

15 Scenario 1: Legacy Monolithic Application Migration

Figure 10: Simplified description of the *Legacy Application* (\mathcal{L}).

We will use the Geospatial Analytics System case to demonstrate the use of the models in an actual migration context. First we used the models to build the *software description* of the *Legacy Application*. A simplified instance of \mathcal{L} in our model is shown in Figure 10.

The given migration scenario attributes led to some preliminary decisions:

- The *Capabilities* are the same in \mathcal{T} and \mathcal{L} , as no new functionality is to be added in this process. A new *Capability Instance* would typically require the introduction of a new *Component Instance* that would REALIZE it, so the migration begins with the initial assumption that the *Component Instances* of \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{T} are expected to be approximately the same, or at least of the same function and type.
- Some of \mathcal{L} 's components, however, have the *Deployment Constraint* “On-premises Software”. This requirement clashes with the global *Deployment Constraints* of \mathcal{E} (and hence of \mathcal{T}), which from its Type “Cloud Platform” includes the requirement “Cloud Compatibility”. As a result, \mathcal{T} will be composed of a part of \mathcal{L} remaining on-premise, and the part that will be migrated (\mathcal{M}).
- The decision to migrate to the cloud also includes the decision that the components of \mathcal{T} will have to be individually accessible via REST/HTTP.

- The constraints of the particular \mathcal{E} include the restriction of using only “Free and Open-Source Software” (FOSS) licensed products.

Figure 11: Simplified depiction of the first step in the migration process: the move of GeoServer from the Legacy (highlighted red) environment to the *Target Environment* (\mathcal{E}). This begins the formulation of \mathcal{M} , and shows the areas where adaptation of GeoServer may be required. Also shown are some of the relationships in the *domain knowledge* used in the present example.

This sets up the context for the first step in the migration process: the move of GeoServer into the *Target Environment* (\mathcal{E}), and the step-by-step construction of \mathcal{M} around it. Figure 11 shows the consequences of that step: the component is moved along with its operational context, which involves its links to other components in \mathcal{L} , its role as a member of a Business Logic tier in a Three-Tier Architecture (which leads to the instantiation of a stub of the latter in \mathcal{M}), and the deployment attributes (red background) carried over from \mathcal{L} . Each of these results in a set of possible mismatches: the architecture may be incompatible with \mathcal{M} ; the links to components in \mathcal{L} have to be made compatible with the fact that the communication now takes place between two different deployment environments, or be replaced one by one with analogous solutions offered by \mathcal{E} (shown as *Application* domain instances on blue background) or from off-the-

shelf products (shown on yellow background); and the component’s deployment attributes may have to be matched with the requirements of \mathcal{E} (blue background around the target application stub).

As a specific example of the adaptation process, we will use the discovery of a suitable cloud-deployed database component to link with GeoServer and implement \mathcal{M} ’s Storage Tier. A simple matching query showed that our previous database, Oracle DB (extended with Oracle Spatial and Graph), was not among \mathcal{E} ’s offerings, meaning that we had to find an alternative. From GeoServer’s documentation⁶, we had a relatively rich *software description* of links to various data storage offerings. A simplified example of some of these links is given in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Partial description of GeoServer’s relations to select *knowledge domain*-level elements and other applications via plugins

Oracle DB is of the *Application Type* “Object-Relational Database”, so we first look for equivalent solutions among \mathcal{E} ’s offerings that were of the same type as Oracle DB ($? \xrightarrow{\text{TYPE OF}} () \xleftarrow{\text{TYPE OF}}$ Oracle DB), which returned PostgreSQL. In order for PostgreSQL to occupy the slot held by OracleDB + Oracle Spatial and Graph, it must fulfill the same role and requirements, such as connecting with GeoServer and supporting the storage and handling of GIS Data formats (its compatibility with \mathcal{E} is a given).

A query on the *Technology* links between GeoServer and PostgreSQL resulted in two possible solutions, shown in Figure 11: the PostGIS and PostgREST plugins. The query results show both the explicit compatibility (COMPATIBLE relationship), known from their documentation, between PostGIS and GeoServer, as well as the implicit compatibility through the use of common *Technology Domain Instances*. This means that even in the absence of

⁶<http://docs.geoserver.org/>

an explicit documentation, a link is still suggested through set matching. The PostgreSQL + PostgREST combination could not be used to replace Oracle DB because neither provides support for GIS data; PostGIS fulfilled that requirement, but failed the \mathcal{E} requirement that only FOSS third-party products can be deployed there, as it has a GNU GPL license.

Since the previous combinations could not be used, we moved one level up and looked for less strictly similar solutions, going to the generic “Database” type. Of the database solutions that are hosted in \mathcal{E} and hence immediately available to us, only the “Object Store” solutions were compatible with the kind of data we wanted to persist. From GeoServer’s documentation, furthermore, we knew that the GeoWebCache component is compatible with the Amazon S3 blob, hence we chose that as our solution.

This is a typical example of how the model can be used in practice. The query-and-match approach is simple to understand and effective in discovering solutions that match the constraints and attributes we set as requirements, particularly if the matching can be automated and executed in parallel along multiple requirement paths in the background. As seen in this case, the model permits filtering out incompatible offerings based on the constraints and features included in \mathcal{T} .

If a solution of the exact type and attributes required is not found, the search can be extended to the set of solutions with mismatches, where we use the *domain knowledge* to attempt to resolve the mismatches, or going up the up along the hierarchy tree(s) to find the nearest similar solution(s). The type hierarchies and domains allow the discovery of connections as well as incompatibilities between software products that are not explicitly documented, by querying along the typologies and the *Technology*, *Capabilities*, and *Constraints* domains. This trial-and-error approach creates a decision tree that can be traversed and altered, and a clearly defined decision context, which can be easily documented.

In our case studies, the usable experimentation space for this process extends at most two to four steps up the hierarchy or along the domain paths; anything more is either too generic or too impractical to implement. If no suitable solution is found within this space, then the same process can be repeated by looking into solutions involving longer paths between the elements, and/or across different domains. This moves the experimentation beyond the search for extant solutions, however, and entails conceptual examination of the system and customized solutions; for example, by looking at the “Enterprise Integration Patterns” set in the *Architecture* domain and deciding that. In practice, such steps were found to be hard to undertake with the model directly, meaning that either an automated guidance in the form of some tooling, or some pre-arranged guidelines in the form of templates are necessary.

16 Scenario 2: System Migration including Architecture Evolution

The previous examples have already made use of “placeholders” during the evolution process: e.g., when we search for a replacement of Oracle DB, we are looking for an element that has some of the same attributes, but whose identity and internal structure is unknown at the moment. This allows the development to proceed even when the exact implementation, in terms of a component’s own *Component Instances* and *Architecture Instances* has not been defined yet, or when it is not our job to define it, for instance in a typical scenario where a generic application for interacting with a specific system can be defined (*compliance-by-design*), leaving the details of its implementation for the various vendors to decide. As long as a component’s *software description* provides the associations of each application element to all other domain elements (e.g., compatible data input/output formats and sources, protocols, functionalities, licenses, etc.), the application itself can be reused.

In the second system we examined (the Water Management System), we were confronted with the need to perform a heavily architecture-centric evolution; thus we imported the comprehensive set of patterns that are related to the Microservice Architecture paradigm described at [24] into our model, describing their interrelations, constraints, and linking them to elements from other domains. However, the correct use of this knowledge proved too complex for practitioners unfamiliar with Microservices. As a result, we turned to defining various templates for commonly occurring pattern combinations. An example is shown in Figure 17, for a Microservice-based application using the “Database per Service” and “Decomposition by Business Capability” *Architecture Patterns*. The template provides a certain type, number, and structure of *Component Instances*, leaving the rest optional. For example, in the Microservice type which implements the “Database per Service” pattern, the business logic (an otherwise undefined placeholder) must be connected to a database (placeholder of type “Database”). Similarly, in the Microservice Application type, we can see how specific components can be tied to certain attributes. In this case, each Microservice *Component Instance* realizes exactly one *Capability*, and the API Gateway needs to be accessible via HTTP/REST.

The migration process is similar to that demonstrated in the previous section. However, the use of the “Decomposition by Business Capability” *Architecture Pattern* required a first stage where the *Capabilities* to be migrated into individual Microservices were identified. In practice, this involved a decomposition of \mathcal{L} until the *Component Instances* or sets thereof that *REALIZE* these *Capabilities* could be identified. This is shown in simplified form in Figure 13. The *Capability* “Data Persistence” is provided by the database component of the Microservice architecture for each microservice, while Data Visualization will be provided by a Dashboard that connects to the API Gateway of the new application. Therefore the main functional capabilities are “Process Orchestration” and “Datasource Management”, *REALIZED* by the Orchestrator component, and

specific technology), or adapting the component’s own implementation to suit the new environment (out of scope for this model).

The ability to provide guidance in implementing an architecture is also important; the architecture templates provided should be flexible enough to serve as a guideline, but allow the architect the freedom to adopt variations or anti-patterns.

17 Scenario 3: Extension to Edge Modelling

In the same manner that we used for the *software description*, we can also provide a *host description* that defines the properties of each host. The set of these descriptions will then constitute a new *deployment* model, operating parallel to the extant *knowledge domain* and *software description* models. Each application can then be associated with (i.e., deployed) to one or more host nodes. In addition, to each such association (runtime deployment) can be associated another node that contains metadata on the deployment, e.g. the service endpoint and protocol, runtime metrics such as CPU load or memory consumption, etc. Even if the association between an application and a host is terminated, the intermediary node will remain and retain the information relevant to the deployment instance.

We have tested this approach in the Data-Driven Automatic Deployment (DDAD) framework, which uses the model information on the application and the available resources, as well as the gathered metrics, to optimize the deployment of applications to the cloud and/or edge platform. An example is the deployment of the *RClassifier* component (RC), depicted in Figure 14.

RC_{Consts} are matched with the platform capabilities \mathcal{P}_{Capabs} to determine the appropriate platform; RC_{Comps} are queried for their dependencies and matched with platform offerings \mathcal{P}_{Comps} to determine which platform nodes offer an appropriate deployment environment; and finally the hardware requirements (RC_{HWReqs}) are matched with the resources provided by each node to determine the deployment location via an optimization algorithm.

The same scenario also illustrates an enhanced selection-by-capability use of the model from a business-driven *software ecosystem* perspective: determining the best library or libraries to use in RC. RC needs to monitor the performance of various elements, and create a classification model. From the *Capabilities* domain, multiple solutions (algorithms and models) offer themselves. *Random Forest* is selected because it is well understood and widely used (*external decision*). The next step concerns selecting one of the available R packages that offer the functionality. As shown in Figure 15, there are two main options: *randomForest* and *randomForestSRC*, as well as *caret*, which aggregates a number of packages related to machine learning. For reasons of performance *caret* is not suitable, as it depends on too many other packages, and offers additional functions that are not really required. Selecting between *randomForest* and *randomForestSRC* is determined by additional metadata that reflect their position in the ecosystem (denoted in blue). Thus *randomForest* is more widely used

Figure 14: Simplified description of the deployment matching process in the DDAD framework.

(over ten times as many downloads), and appears to be the standard implementation in the R ecosystem, it being reused by other aggregate packages such as *caret*. It is more frequently maintained than *randomForestSRC* (although this may also be a factor of instability), and its latest version is considerably smaller in code size than the latest version of *randomForestSRC*. Other metadata not shown here that are useful could be the frequency of bugs and the average time before they are addressed, the existence of tutorials and supporting material, and even the identity of the developers of each package—packages contributed by more experienced and active developers are likely to be of higher quality.

18 Managing the Complexity

The models are able to provide a standardized method to describe applications with considerable degree of detail, as well as the context of software evolution and migration into new platforms. The links between *software description* and *domain knowledge* also allow queries that can find implicit relationships between domain instances and find solutions for adaptation problems (RQ3). In practice, however, the very expressiveness of the model became a disadvantage when practitioners were called upon to use it directly.

As can be seen in Figure 16, the complexity of a single *Architecture Style*, in this case that of microservices, can be overwhelming. One option, which we are currently pursuing, is to hide the complexity by building abstraction layers on

Figure 15: Partial description of the R ecosystem’s offerings in the *machine learning* domain, as used in the DDAD framework.

top of the model, and giving it as a tool to the practitioner; the tool’s business logic would use context to determine the relevant model instances, hiding the rest.

Another option, which we built using our model, was to guide the practitioner through templates of common and/or recommended configurations, with placeholders to be filled out as required, thus extending the application of the “minimal” *software description* mentioned above. An example is given in Figure 17, making use of the same elements as found in Figure 16.

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Figure 16: Simplified representation of the *Microservice Architecture* style, its component patterns, and select connections to the other domains

Figure 17: Example of a template for a Microservice-based application: the application has a number of microservices that each fulfill a specific business capability, and have their own database each. The options for the use of a “Microservice Chassis” component and the choice of the microservices’ communication pattern(s) have been left open. For ease of presentation, the collections and root node of the *software description* are not shown.